

The Resurgence of Unipolarity within Multipolar Trends: Deconstructing Necropolitics and Its Global Impacts

Author-Jajnadatta Pattanayak, Assistant Professor (contractual),
Berhampur University, Odisha, India

ABSTRACT

This study will showcase the resurgence of power dynamics in contemporary and its impacts on the interactions among nation states at international affairs. The dynamics of world politics are changing more dramatically than we might expect, making the future increasingly unpredictable. In the 21st century, we are witnessing a geopolitical juggernaut characterized by civil wars, invasions, regime changes, political turmoil, border conflicts, democratic backsliding, the rise of authoritarianism, food shortages, water scarcity, and deadly pandemics like Covid-19 and Ebola etc. Additionally, acute climate challenges and declining fertility rates further complicate and rising concerns in the global landscape. The unpredictable nature of geopolitics reveals the profound changes occurring in global phenomena. Now, it is pretty difficult to predict the strategies of major countries as they navigate this new international order, emphasizing survival in a world dominated by statism, self-help, and survival, as described in Neorealism.

KEYWORDS: Power, Juggernaut, Regime, climate, Statism, Self Help, Survival.

INTRODUCTION

Every nation and individual must learn from their history, yet often this learning remains in halfway. Karl Marx, a prominent thinker in western world, famously stated, "History always repeats itself, first as tragedy, second as farce." We are currently witnessing this phenomenological geopolitical plate tectonic in geopolitics, particularly in regions like Ukraine-Russia, Israel-Palestine, Thailand –Cambodia, Armenia-Azerbaijan, China-Taiwan and India-Pakistan etc. The term "Necropolitics" refers to 'the politics of death' and has a rather grim connotation within the global community can be applicable to the contemporary conflicts and the

rising death of the common innocent civilians. The prefix 'Necro' relates to death or corpses, while politics signifies the everyday affairs of state. Cameroonian historian Achille Mbembe coined the term in an essay "Nécropolitique" in French published in 2002. In recent years, the concept has gained momentum as nations increasingly employ this dark form of politics, as discussed in Nai's (2023) book, called "Dark Politics: The Personality of Politicians and the Future of Democracy", which highlights the dark side of nations at particular historical moments. Over the last century, huge numbers of wars have been fought, and the repercussions of the First and Second World Wars have significantly altered the global landscape more than our expectations. The world seems to be drifting towards a potential Third World War, which appears inevitable unless current trends change. Looking on this issue once Albert Einstein famously remarked, "I know not with what weapons World War III will be fought, but World War IV will be fought with sticks and stones." This perspective is increasingly observable in today's geopolitical climate, especially concerning warmongering nature of the nation-states.

REVIVAL OF NEO-REALISM

'Statism, 'Self-Help, and 'Survival, are the three cardinal components of the theory of Neo-Realism given by Kenneth Waltz in his book called *Man, the State, and War* (1959) and *Theory of International Politics* (1979). Realism and Neo-Realism manifests as a practical, rather than philosophical, concept focused on national survival. Here, we see the saying, "Freedom for the pike is the death of minnows": one must perish for others to survive. This reality reflects international phenomena where more powerful nations exploit smaller, underdeveloped nations. According to Kenneth Waltz, a leading figure in international neo-realism, the global order is chaotic and anarchic. Nations strive for survival, self-help, and statism, which cannot be overlooked. The rise of rivalries among superpowers disrupts the geopolitical order. A significant geopolitical shift that underscores the unpredictability of international relations as articulated as Black Swan theory by Nassim Nicholas Taleb, a Lebanese-American essayist, mathematical statistician, former options trader, risk analyst, and aphorist., the rise of authoritarianism, food shortages, water scarcity, and deadly pandemics like COVID-19 and Ebola. Additionally, acute climate challenges and declining fertility rates further complicate the global landscape. It indicates analysis will cover major countries' approaches to this new global

order and their strategies for survival in a world dominated by statism, survival, and self-help, as described in Neo-realism.

REINSTATEMENT OF MUNROE DOCTRINE

These evolving challenges across the world raise questions about strategic autonomy and state sovereignty. The Donald Trump administration trying hard to rejuvenate and revive the past glory and supremacy by which he can transform a declining superpower to a great power again. Trump 2.0 seeks to revive the Monroe Doctrine of 1823, which opposed European colonialism in the Western Hemisphere, by urging others to embrace the "Make America Great Again" (MAGA) agenda. Countries in the Americas are currently experiencing illusions due to strict policies and tariff actions. The United States Agency for International Development (USAID) has come under scrutiny for questionable transactions that they have done in past, raising concerns about the previous administration's efforts to use aid to shape the political landscape in multiple countries. The Trump administration has already introduced volatility in global stock markets, leading to investor skepticism as they witness significant declines. These mounting challenges raise questions on strategic autonomy and state sovereignty. In Saudi Arabia and the first round of peace negotiations between Ukraine and Russia took place, though progress was hindered by President Zelenskyy's reluctance to end the war. Conversely, Russia currently finds itself in a favorable position, especially because following the events of 2014 when it took control of Crimea, creating a paradoxical situation. On February 24, 2024, the Russian military initiated a special operation in Ukraine, posing a potential threat to NATO, the Western-led military organization. The 2025 presidential election shocked global leaders as Donald Trump rose to power once again for the second time. A business tycoon and reality television star with no prior political or military experience, Trump has now won two non-consecutive terms. His domestic and foreign policies are expected to leave a significant mark on the USA administration. His unique approach to political decision-making sets him apart from other presidents, making his tenure a crucial period for insights into contemporary geopolitical scenario. Although U.S. hegemony appears to have declined in this multipolar world, the United States remains the world's largest economy, with technological supremacy and considerable military and cultural influence. The effects of war, inflation, COVID-19, and food shortages create a series of global shockwaves. This article will analyze how Trump's executive decisions

are reshaping the world order, emphasizing the importance of foreign policy while sidelining domestic politics.

EURASIA

Ukraine, once called the breadbasket of Europe, produces a significant portion of food grains, mainly wheat, feeding many around the world. However, following the special military operation launched by Russia on February 25, 2022, the food supply chain and agricultural security have come to a halt. The war and conflicts between neighboring countries directly disrupt the international order. Most of the eastern regions of Ukraine—such as Donetsk, Luhansk, Zaporizhzhia, and Kharkiv—are now under Russian occupation. Although the International Criminal Court has issued an arrest warrant, its authority is being undermined. The endgame remains undefined, ceasefire appears distant, mass killings continue, and territorial sovereignty is threatened in the conflict between Russia and Ukraine. Security issues have disrupted the transport of food, fertilizers, and fuel. Prices are fluctuating, and essential fertilizers for farmers cannot reach them. The last meeting between Put and Trump held on August 15, 2025, at Joint Base Elmendorf–Richardson in Anchorage, Alaska somehow fuelled AND show a new horizon for the peace in upcoming time, as a result a 28 point programme on the way to end the long lasting conflict. But more or less the European security has been compromised, the balance of power becoming balance of terror and a sense of threat perception that we are calling security dilemma deeply clouding over the head of the European leaders. Eventually the future of Eurasia lies in the hands of the mature leaders and their approach towards the world and peace at last. India's Prime Minister has stated, "This is not the era of war," symbolizing India's stance in the current international landscape of international politics. While India promotes the idea of "Vishva Bandhu," it finds it challenging to strike a balance between the two warring nations. Regarding the Middle East and the Palestine-Israel conflict, India maintains a consistent position. It always supports the two-nation theory, which acknowledges both sides and respects their territorial sovereignty. Initially, India advocated for the creation of a full-fledged Palestine before 2000's. However, due to India's interdependence and deep engagement with Israel, it has shifted toward the two-nation theory, with Israel remaining a reliable partner over time. Both Israel and Palestine maintain cordial relations with India, as do Ukraine and Russia. Even during the

ongoing crisis in Europe, the Indian Prime Minister visited both countries. India navigates this interdependent world, recognizing that in international relations no nation can survive in isolation. Thankfully, most Indian students studying in Ukraine have been successfully evacuated without casualties, through an operation known as "Operation Ganga." So, what about Russia? The relationship is long-standing and continues to evolve, experiencing ups and downs over time.

Source: ACLED 2025

MIDDLE EAST

Trump's approach to Iran's nuclear program has involved a mix of sanctions, military threats, and diplomatic efforts. These strategies have escalated more tensions and resulted in such a complex, ongoing negotiations. His executive order in May 2018 to withdraw the USA from the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) marked a significant shift, especially considering Iran's missile program. The JCPOA, also known as the Iran Nuclear Deal, was established to limit Iran's nuclear ambitions and programme in exchange for the easing of sanctions and other provisions. This agreement was finalized in Vienna on July 14, 2015, among Iran and the P5+1 country, along with the European Union. During the Trump administration, the USA emphasized targeting both Iran and North Korea due to their involvement in uranium enrichment. Following

the US withdrawal from the JCPOA in 2018, Iran faced severe economic sanctions with heavy political pressure. Trump's objective has been to force Iran to negotiate a more comprehensive agreement, insisting on a complete halt to its uranium enrichment program. However, Iran has firmly rejected these imposed demands with asserting it has the right to continue uranium enrichment programme for peaceful and civilian purposes only. In the US, public sentiment increasingly leans toward resolving the rising disputes through diplomatic means rather than military intervention or harsh sanctions. European nations including Russia have made attempts to mediate and revive the JCPOA framework but have had limited success achieved yet. The USA's unilateral approach complicates the situation further. In what is described as Trump's 2.0 period, he has actively pursued a successful deal. However, achieving a peaceful resolution through diplomacy will pose considerable challenges for his administration. Several discussions between the leaders of the two nations have taken place. Trump, known for his accomplishments as a businessman, now has got a chance to establish him as one of the most significant leaders in US history by successfully navigating this deal. Recently, the US conducted airstrikes on three nuclear sites inside—Natanz, Isfahan, and Fordow—in an attempt to disrupt Iran's nuclear program. Unfortunately, the bunker-buster bombs used in these strikes failed to detonate those sites and remain half harmed. This situation is likely to escalate tensions further between Iran and Israel, with potential repercussions for the strategically important Strait of Hormuz. Trump has proposed transforming Gaza into the "Riviera of the West Asia." West Asia is becoming increasingly tense due to the power struggles among state and non-state actors. Moreover, a new front has emerged for Putin in Syria, where separatist militia groups have taken control of Aleppo, the country's second-largest ancient city, while Damascus has fallen into the hands of Ahmed al-Sharaa. On one front, Russia, Iran, and Syria are engaged in conflict against Israel and Turkey-backed militias in the region, providing indirect support to three radical groups collectively known as the "three H's": Hezbollah, Hamas, and Houthi. The doomsday clock is ticking, serving as a reminder to the global community of the imminent threat of catastrophic events. Iran's nuclear program has gained momentum, while Russia has deployed mid-range intercontinental strategic non-nuclear warheads—capable of Multiple Independently Targetable Reentry Vehicles (MIRV's) and Orensik nuclear capable missiles in both Russian and Belarusian soil raising fears of a potential nuclear escalation in the near future. The situation in Ukraine, often referred to as the "breadbasket of Europe," is now precarious, particularly following the

sabotage of the Nord Stream gas Pipeline -II, which has disrupted the flow of affordable gas from Russia to European countries. Trump's "Drill, Baby, Drill" campaign may have been intended as a prelude to a high-profile state visit to Saudi Arabia, where the headlines may focus on violence and bloodshed. Just when it seemed the world had reached a saturation point, new conflicts emerge, with economic implications for US consumers as tensions manifest not only in violence but also in trade disputes. In Asia, the region teeters on the brink of democratic shift. A strong democracy like South Korea recently imposed martial law, which was ultimately lifted following significant pressure from the public and opposition parties. The Indo-China region remains a focal point due to rampant aggressive actions from China, including salami slicing, "wolf warrior" and cheek book diplomacy. Conversely, recent border settlements between China and India raise questions about China's assertiveness.

Source:ACLED 2025

PALESTINE

The genesis of the crisis in Palestine can be traced back to the Sykes-Picot Agreement and the Balfour Declaration. The first was signed in 1916 between the United Kingdom and France to acknowledge the possibility of an independent Arab state or confederation while disregarding any prior arrangements for a Jewish homeland in Palestine. The Balfour Declaration, signed in 1917, formalized the United Kingdom's support for the establishment of a Jewish homeland, leading to tensions in the region. It is undeniable that European powers and their colonial policies have distorted the international political landscape forever. The cases of Israel-Palestine and India-Pakistan, along with the Occupation of Diego Garcia and control over the Falkland

Islands in South America, serve as prominent examples. The creation of Israel as an independent nation-state amidst distinct religious and ethnic neighbors resulted in a complex and confrontational environment. The UN has estimated that more than 1,300 Palestinians have been killed at food centers since May 2025. Despite mounting international outrage and allegations of war crimes, and Hamas's acceptance of the latest ceasefire proposal put forward by Qatar and Egypt, Israel has intensified its attacks on Gaza City in preparation for a new offensive. But somehow with the efforts of USA, Israel agreed upon a truce cum ceasefire after a fruitful intergovernmental meeting with most of the Arab Nations themed as Peace-2025 on 9th October 2025 in Sharm El Sheikh, Egypt, following an agreement to implement the first phase of the Gaza peace plan to end the Gaza war which began in 2023. What is unfolding in Gaza goes far beyond Israel's stated aims of defeating Hamas and releasing its prisoners. The growing body of evidence suggests intent to destroy Palestinian life and society in Gaza itself. The most brutal crimes are being committed against 2.3 million people—right before the world's eyes. Israel cannot continue its devastation of Gaza any further. In recent years, it seems that the collective West, including European powers and the USA, has been more concerned about Ukraine than about Gaza or the Palestinian people as a whole. Since the formation of Israel in 1948, the Middle East has been a boiling pot. The Palestine Question and its associated problems remain unresolved. The UN has reported that the death toll has surpassed approximately 56,000, including nearly 18,000 children throughout this conflict. This has become a new normal, as violence occurs daily, while so-called superpowers and alternative power centers remain silent on the issue. In contrast, Israel is backed by Western powers, which wish to transform Gaza into the Riviera of West Asia—an idea that is largely imaginary and philosophical. Nonetheless, some Western allies, such as Australia, Canada, France, and the UK, have begun to speak out and criticize Israeli atrocities, recognizing them as acts of mass killing that could be described as genocide. This indicates that the momentum for Palestinian full statehood has gained some support; however, the question remains: at what cost? Currently, out of 193 countries, 147 recognize the existence of Palestine, while an additional 90 countries have expressed support for a two-state solution. The imbalance of power and the resulting power vacuum were fundamental issues facing Palestine in general and Gaza in particular. The power vacuum created by the ouster of Bashar al-Assad in Syria, American strikes on Iranian nuclear facilities, and Russian involvement in the Ukrainian conflict has generated significant instability and chaos in the

region. Palestine is now divided into several segments, including the West Bank, the Gaza Strip, and Jerusalem etc. It is imperative for responsible international actors to address this situation as quickly as possible. International organizations like the UN must take proactive steps to tackle this issue.

Source: UN OCHA

SOUTH ASIA

The Trump era also highlighted the stark reality of diplomatic failures in Bangladesh and surrounding countries. India's temporary suspension of the Indus Water Treaty has altered Pakistan's water sovereignty, granting India an upper hand over the rivers in the Indus River system. However, according to the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, no country has the exclusive right to expel or unilaterally suspend a treaty. Meanwhile after Pehelgam attack the Prime Minister of India reiterated, "Water and blood cannot flow side by side," signifying that Indo-Pak relations still adhere to a status quo principle and gone to the cold chamber. Operations conducted by both countries—such as Operation Sindoor conducted by India which reflect ongoing tensions, with India's stance countering Pakistan's perceived nuclear blackmail after operation Sindoor. The statement that "terror and talks cannot go together; terror and trade cannot go together; water and blood cannot flow together" underscores this point.

GLOBAL SOUTH

In the Arctic, rapid militarization by various power centers is undermining the Ottawa Declaration of 1996, with some studies suggesting that this region could become the next geopolitical battleground. Major Powers are increasingly interested in the Arctic for two main reasons: first, to create and navigate a new transactional trade route; and second, to access untapped natural resources like rare earth materials, natural gas, and petroleum. However, achieving this may only be possible with the complete melting of the glaciers. We are currently witnessing significant environmental degradation across the world, which could lead to new opportunities in the Arctic for nations eager to exploit resources. As seen in recent geopolitical maneuvers, countries are racing to legitimize their claims over these untapped natural resources. So that, the United States has expressed interest in acquiring Greenland from Denmark for greater access to Arctic resources. Simultaneously, Russia is advancing the use of giant icebreakers to navigate these waters. The COP-29 conference, hosted by a Global South country, yielded a mixed outcome; the Baku Declaration was only partially successful as Western countries agreed to provide \$300 million for climate mitigation efforts—just the tip of the iceberg. Countries must address the need to protect our planet based on the principle of "National Interest with International Responsibility"(NIIR). The Prime Minister of India aptly noted that "this is not the era of war," emphasizing the necessity for sensitivity, maturity, and the pursuit of a better and peaceful world order.

CONCLUSION

This study, after analyzing and verifying all the relevant issues, suggests that the world is moving towards unprecedented consequences that we never expected. Ultimately, every nation must maintain a minimum level of maturity and resilience in its decision-making to foster a non-antagonistic world order. Multiple continents across the world are facing a change in power dynamics, which is obvious, but it should be done without hampering the interests of others. The role of international actors is also crucial, because they are the pivotal agencies and arrangements that can save people from the hellish scenario we are witnessing in today's contemporary world.

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